

AI COLLABORATORS

AI collaborators refer to the different roles an AI system can play within a human-AI collaboration.

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User autonomy

AI authority

THE ASSISTANT

The AI system is regarded as an assistant, as it supports its end-users in fulfilling their actions. It provides useful information at the right moment.

User autonomy

AI authority

THE GUIDE

The AI system is seen as a guide, as it gives clear instructions and directs the end-user to help them to reach their goals.

User autonomy

AI authority

THE ADVISOR

The AI system is seen as an advisor, as it proposes possible actions to its end-users. The end-users can choose to accept these actions or reject them.

User autonomy

AI authority

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TRUST ENABLERS

Enablers are AI characteristics that can increase the feeling of trust in AI systems.

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TRANSPARENCY

“I can explain you very clearly how I was designed, developed and deployed. I know exactly what my limitations and benefits are and what potential biases I may have.”

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EMPATHY

“I can sense your emotions and respond to them as if I am a human-being.”

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RELIABILITY

“I perform consistently and accurately across changing conditions (e.g. co-workers, changing parameters, context) and over time.”

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EXPLAINABILITY

“I can clearly explain why I made a certain decision or what output I have produced.”

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ETHICALLY

“I reduce issues of misuse, prevent prejudices and respect human consent and therefore protect your privacy, safety and other implications I might have on you.”

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PRIVACY

“I only collect and use (your) data that is absolutely necessary for me to function. I keep this data safe, and I don’t share it with anyone else.”

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ACCURACY

“I am correct and precise in the output that I produce.”

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CONTROLLABILITY

"I allow my decisions and output to be overridden by you when necessary."

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SYSTEM ATTRIBUTES

Attributes allow AI systems to interact, work together, and adjust efficiently in changing environments. They enhance the usability and significance of AI systems for end-users.

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SENSING

“I can interpret the environment and context I’m used in to better understand and assist you more clearly.”

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PREDICTABILITY

“I can behave in a way that is expected of me, because I can investigate and analyse (future) trends, activities and behaviours of the process and you.”

DIRECTIVITY

“I direct your attention to critical features, suggestions, and warnings that I have encountered.”

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DIRECTABILITY

"I follow your commands and guidance to complete my tasks."

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ADAPTABILITY

“I can easily adjust my parameters, behaviour, and/or output when elements in my environment are changing or when different information (by you) is given to me.”

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AWARENESS SHARING

“I communicate and exchange information and data-driven insights I have learned with you so we can collaborate better together and improve the outcomes of our collaboration.”

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CUSTOMISABILITY

“I am input-sensitive, I follow the commands you give me, the settings you set, and I work based on your indicated preferences.”

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TRACEABILITY

“I record everything, and I can tell you at any moment everything about a particular process, specifications, changes and similar.”

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CAPABILITIES

Capabilities refer to the tasks or functions that an AI system can perform exceptionally well, particularly in scenarios where the AI assists humans in a collaborative setting.

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RECOGNITION

“I recognise patterns, concepts, or objects from information sources (i.e. data).”

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PREDICTION

“I forecast the future by analysing and interpreting historical data (i.e. data collected about past events and actions).”

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REASONING

“I process information and make decisions.”

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GENERATION

“I combine existing inputs and create new content (i.e. designs, text, images, code, ...).”

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RECOMMENDATION

“I recommend things based on previous information or behaviours if I think it might be useful or helpful for you.”

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COLLABORATION QUALITIES

Qualities are the essential characteristics that make a human-AI collaboration comfortable and distinguishable.

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CLARITY

“I feature a clear interface with elements that are easy for you to use and understand.”

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FAMILIARITY

“I have an intuitive look and feel, allowing you to navigate my system in a natural way without a long training.”

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ERGONOMICS

“I am fitting into my environment, and I am adjusted to you so that I am comfortable to use both physically and cognitively.”

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RESPONSIVENESS

“I respond swiftly when I am given commands.”

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CONSISTENCY

“I respond with the same results every time you give me the same command.”

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GUIDANCE

“I give you all the information you need about my features so you can use me as easy as possible.”

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TONE OF VOICE

Tone of voice refers to the way the AI-system is speaking to the user and communicating its personality.

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MORE FORMAL

“I communicate in accordance with conventional requirements.”

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MORE SERIOUS

“I am earnest and weighty in my communication.”

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MORE RESPECTFUL

“I show politeness and courtesy
in my communication.”

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MORE STRAIGHTFORWARD

“I communicate in a dry and to the point way.”

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MORE CASUAL

“I express myself in a spontaneous and conversational way.”

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MORE FUNNY

“I attempt to communicate in a more humorous way.”

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MORE IRREVERENT

“I am cheeky or offensive about the subject I’m communicating about.”

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MORE ENTHUSIASTIC

“I am excited about the information I am conveying.”

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MORE SIMPLE

“I speak your language; I explain things in an accessible way”

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MORE COMPLEX

“I explain things in-depth and with a lot of detail.”

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ADJUSTABLE

“Depending on your needs or how you feel, I can adjust my way of talking or the information I give.”

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INTERFACE TYPES

Interface types refer to the medium through which the human and the AI system can collaborate. A system can use a combination of different interface types, both for giving information and receiving commands.

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VISUAL COMMANDS

“You can give me commands in a graphic and/or textual way via a screen or projection.”

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VISUAL INFORMATION

“I present information in a graphic and/or textual way via a screen or projection.”

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AUDITORY COMMANDS

“You can give me commands in an auditory way using voice and/or sounds.”

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AUDITORY INFORMATION

“I give information in an auditory way using voice and/or sounds.”

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HAPTIC COMMANDS

“I respond to commands that are based on movement, such as gestures or body postures.”

HAPTIC INFORMATION

“I provide information through clues that you can feel, such as vibrations or force feedback.”

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